

THE CONCEPT OF TOLERANCE DESCRIBED IN THE LYRICAL NOVEL THE KINDNESS OF ENEMIES BY LEILA ABOULELA

¹Muxtasarxon Azimova Jaloldin qizi,

²Dildora Qurbonova Alisher qizi

Uzbekistan State World Languages University.

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Annotation: This article is about the lyrical novel of «The Kindness of Enemies» by Leila Aboulela. Mainly, in the article mentioned its published dates, reviews of the book. Also, it is described the life of Muslims in that centuries, events that happened during the Caucasian War.

Key words: Tolerance, Muslims, jihad, sword, Caucasian War, professor, half-Russian, half-Sudanese.

"The Kindness of Enemies" was written by Leila Aboulela and published in 2015. The Kindness of Enemies depicts the story of a half-Russian, half-Sudanese professor who embarks on a journey to document the professor of a Muslim historical figure, Imam Shamil, who gained notoriety through his leading role in the anti-Russian resistance movement of the Caucasian War. Set in 2010, the book also tackles the theme of life as a Muslim in the post-9/11 era.

The lives of modern-day Muslims living in Britain and a historical Muslim leader are intertwined in Leila Aboulela's beautifully written novel about identity and belonging.

Leila Aboulela's 2015 book *The Kindness of Enemies* follows Natasha Wilson on a powerful journey that spans time and continents. Natasha, a half-Sudanese, half-Russian history professor is researching Imam Shamil, a nineteenth-century Muslim leader who headed the anti-Russian resistance during the Caucasian War. Natasha soon discovers that her student Osama is a descendant of Imam Shamil and possesses his legendary sword. We are then given access to Imam's story. A complex tale of faith, history, nationality, and politics, *The Kindness of Enemies* breathes life into legend and provides an important examination of the experience of Muslims in a post-9/11 world.

Natasha Wilson, born Natasha Hussein to a Sudanese father and a Russian mother in Khartoum, works at a Scottish university; the nineteenth-century Caucasian War is her specialty. The war, we learn, witnessed a fierce Muslim resistance to the Russian invasion of Chechnya, Dagestan, and Circassia. In her mid-30s, Natasha is overweight. Her mother has recently died, her relationships with men have ended badly, and she has recently had an abortion.

Natasha soon discovers that one of her students, Osama Raja, who goes by "Oz," has in his possession the sword of Imam Shamil, a great leader in the forces of resistance. Natasha visits Oz and his mother, Malak's home to see it. They reveal

to Natasha that they are descendants of Shamil. The gorgeous curved sword is mounted on the wall and has the word “Allah” inscribed on it in gold. They get into a discussion about jihad and Sufism. Natasha asks Malak if she knows that Queen Victoria supported Shamil. Malak responds that Queen Victoria championed a jihad. Oz says she should not be naïve; if the Russians had overtaken the Caucasus, India would have been threatened.

Malak argues that jihad is a spiritual, internal struggle, but it has become synonymous with terrorism since the 9/11 attacks. She blames the Salafists and Wahabis for this. Oz, however, contends that limiting jihad by characterizing it as an internal struggle has turned into a bandwagon every pacifist Muslim has climbed onto. “You Sufis,” he asserts, “play down your historical role in jihad.

Snow begins to fall during Natasha’s visit, and Oz and Malak invite her to stay. She spends two nights at their house. However, we then learn that Oz has been using the email username “Sword Of Shamil” to message Natasha with subject lines such as “Weapons used for Jihad.” Oz is arrested and dragged from his mother’s house in an early morning raid conducted by security services. They also take cell phones, laptops, CDs, and the sword of Shamil. When Natasha returns home, she finds her flat has been burgled, and she moves to a hotel.

The author then introduces a parallel storyline set in Caucasian Georgia in 1854. Imam Shamil’s son, Jamaleldin, was taken and has been held captive by the Russians as the tsar’s special guest since 1839. Jamaleldin cannot help but enjoy the life he develops in St. Petersburg, Russia, where he is raised as a Russian officer and a gentleman. Tsar Nicholas I asks Jamaleldin to rule Chechnya and Dagestan on his behalf.

Shamil, however, is determined to get his son back, and in 1854, he leads the Lezgins, a fearsome tribe that follows him, in an attack against the Georgian estate of Tsinondali. There, they capture the granddaughter of the last Georgian king, Princess Anna Elinichna, her two children Alexander and Lydia, and a French governess, Madame Drancey, who are taken as hostages. Shamil has a plan to exchange the captives for his son. During the frightening horseback abduction, Lydia is killed.

Imam Shamil welcomes Anna as a guest, but she is still a captive there. Anna befriends two of Shamil’s three wives, but his first wife treats her with suspicion and severity. Anna also develops a rapport with Shamil, the two appreciating one another’s qualities. If not comfortable, Anna at least comes to feel acclimated to her captors. The possibility is introduced that if the exchange of captives breaks down, Shamil may take Anna as his wife. The idea of returning to his father after fifteen years in Russia evokes a crisis of loyalty and identity for

Jamaleldin.

Back in the present, Natasha learns from her mother's best friend, Grusha, that Natasha's estranged father, who is back in Khartoum, is dangerously ill. He had abandoned her when he divorced Natasha's mother, and he stayed behind when Natasha moved to Scotland with her mother and stepfather. Later, he speaks to her on the phone, telling her he wishes he had fought harder to keep her with him. She reminisces about Grusha's son Yasha, who was her first boyfriend. Yasha's wife and daughter had been killed in a plane crash a few years prior. Natasha decides to return to Khartoum for the first time in twenty years.

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